

ISic1183

I.Sicily inscription 1183

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Apollonia

Place of origin (modern)

Monte San Fratello

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Monte San Fratello

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140666

1. Χαρίτων έπο [ίησε — — —]
2. ΠΟΝ τόν καλο [κοίμητον(?)]
3. Όρφιτιανόν ΙΕ [— — — —]
4. ΔΟΥΛΟ έν [θ]εώ τε [λευτήσαντα]
- 5.

Edition: PHI140667

1. δοϋλο[ς] Νεωτε [ρίου]
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492788

EDCS 39102337

PHI 140666

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Bibliography

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